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Human Rights in Nigeria's Cyberspace: A Critical Appraisal

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ABSTRACT

Human rights in cyberspace concern the application of fundamental rights and freedoms to online environments in the same manner as in physical space. This paper examines the applicability of human rights in Nigeria's cyberspace, focusing on whether constitutional, statutory, regional, and international human rights norms extend to digital activities. Using a doctrinal research methodology, the paper finds that the human rights provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), including rights to privacy, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, freedom of expression, assembly and association, freedom from discrimination, and other related rights apply fully in cyberspace. It further establishes that other national laws, such as the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act 1983 and the Child Rights Act 2003, as well as regional, international and customary international law touching on human rights and human rights instruments ratified by Nigeria, are also applicable online. The rights most frequently implicated in cyber-operations in Nigeria are privacy, expression, peaceful assembly and association, freedom from discrimination, and freedom of thought, conscience, and religion. It is concluded that Nigeria's constitutional, regional, and international human rights protections extend to cyberspace, as affirmed by the United Nations and the African Union. However, low public awareness leads to frequent unchecked violations. It is therefore recommended that Chapter Four of Nigeria's Constitution be amended to expressly guarantee a right to internet access, ensuring universal connectivity for the full exercise of human rights online.

Keywords: Human, Human Rights, Cyber Human Rights, Cyberspace.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Cyber human rights are the fundamental rights and freedoms individuals are entitled to enjoy online just as they do offline. They ensure that people can fully participate in the digital space while being protected from abuse and violations; human rights are those rights endowed upon human beings by nature or by their creator by reason of their humanity, which are equally provided, no matter the continent they live, disrespect or repression of which degrade the dignity inherent in human beings to the duration of the disrespect or repression, as they are inextinguishable, inalienable and immutable and therefore not creation of the state or society¹. These rights encompass civil, political, economic, and social freedoms, including the rights to life, dignity, liberty, privacy, fair trial, expression, religion, association, movement, equality, property, education, work, development, self-determination, and access to the common heritage of mankind. They are principally codified in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, forming part of the United Nations Bill of Rights²,

¹ O Akeuseph 'Appraising respect for Human Rights in Nigeria and Iceland; An Exercise en fulfillment and De par?' (2024) (4) (1) *Lagos Bar Journal*, 62.

² Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948, arts 1 – 29.

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights³, and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights⁴.

Cyberspace lacks a universally accepted definition. Although no single, common meaning has been established, scholars have attempted to define it. For instance, Otti and Lorentz describe cyberspace as a time-dependent network of interconnected information systems together with the human users who interact with them⁵.

Their description portrayed cyberspace as an artificial space created by humans for human purposes and in this way acknowledged its implicit human dimension.⁶ It has been expressed that the term ‘cyberspace’ is ‘a world-wide virtual space, with many sub-communities, evenly distributed, using a technical environment – first the internet – in which citizens and organizations utilize information and communication technologies for their social, political and commercial interactions⁷.

Cyberspace comprises four core components: physical infrastructure (such as computers, servers, routers, and telecommunications systems), software networks, data and information systems, and the human element that interacts with and operates these technological structures⁸.

On the applicability of International Human Rights Law in cyberspace, the United Nations Human Rights Council has affirmed that international human right law applies in cyberspace; individuals enjoy the same human rights online as they enjoy offline⁹. This position has been re-affirmed by the African Union, and many States such as Australia, Canada, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, New Zealand, Norway United Kingdom, United States¹⁰ and so on. Accordingly, States are therefore bound by their human rights obligations to respect, protect and fulfill human rights in cyberspace¹¹. Nigeria’s human rights obligations in cyberspace derive primarily from treaty law. Having signed and ratified instruments such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, it is legally bound to respect, protect, and fulfill human rights online.

Codified human rights, fundamental rights or natural rights in Nigeria, are majorly found in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) particularly in Sections 33 – 44¹², African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act 1983, particularly Articles 1 – 29,¹³ and the Child Rights Act 2003¹⁴; Nigeria is under an obligation to respect, protect and fulfill human rights as codified in International and domestic laws online as well as offline.

This work examines human rights in cyberspace, with particular focus on the enjoyment and violations of the rights to privacy, freedom of expression, and freedom of assembly and association and non discrimination and so on, within Nigeria’s digital space. It also proposes solutions to the challenges affecting the protection and realization of these rights online

³ International Covenant on Civil and Political rights 1966 art 1-27.

⁴ International covenant on Economic, social and culture right 1966, arts 1-15.

⁵ R Otti and P Lorents ‘Cyberspace definition and implications:5th European Conference on Information Management and Evaluation’ <<https://dumitrudumbrava.files.wordpress.com/2012/01/cyberspace-definition-and-implications> > accessed 27 July, 2024.

⁶ P Pavlova, “Human Rights- Based Approach to Cyber Security: Addressing the Security Risks of Targeted Groups (2020) (4)(3) *Peace Human Rights Governance* 395.

⁷ UNESCO: ‘Internet Governance Glossary <<https://en.unesco.org/glossaries/igg/groups/i.%20Internet%20governance%20general> >accessed 27 July, 2024.

⁸ N Tsagourias, ‘The Legal Status of Syberspace in Nicholas K Tsagourias and Russel Buchan (eds), *Research handbook on International Law and Cyberspace* (Edward Elger 2015) 15.

⁹ United Nations General Assembly ‘Reports of Group of Governmental Experts on Advancing Responsible State Behaviour in Cyber space in the context of International Security’14 July, 2021, A/76/135 Para 36; United Nations Human Rights Council, ‘The Promotion, Protection and Enjoyment of Human Rights on the Internet’ Resolution A/HRC/RES/32/13; NATO, Warsaw Summit Communiqué (July 9, 2016), para7a; G8 summit of Deavile, Declaration: Renewed Commitment for Freedom and Democracy (27 May 2011) para 11/II; United Nations General Assembly, ‘Reports of the Group of Government Experts on Developments in the Field of Information and Telecommunication on the context of International Security (22 July, 2015) A/70/174,Paras 13 (e)and 28 (b)..

¹⁰ NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (ccdcoe.org) International Human Rights <<https://cyberlaw.ccdcoe.org>> accessed 27 July,2024.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² Construction of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), ss33-43.

¹³ African Charter on Human and Peoples Right (Ratification and Enforcement) Act 1983, art 1-29.

¹⁴ Child Rights Act 2003.

2.0 Human Rights Implicated in Cyberspace Operations in Nigeria

The human rights that are often implicated in cyberspace operations and indeed in Nigeria's cyberspace include the right to privacy¹⁵, and the right to freedom of opinion and expression¹⁶. Other rights such as right to freedom of assembly and association¹⁷, right to prohibition of discrimination¹⁸, the right to life¹⁹, right to education²⁰, right to work²¹ and other economic and social rights may also be affected by cyber operations or cyber related measures²². If the right in question is absolute such as the right to be free from torture or slavery, then, no interference with it is allowed²³.

This work focuses on the rights to privacy, freedom of expression, assembly and association, religion, and freedom from discrimination in cyberspace.

a. The Plight to Privacy

In Nigeria, the right to privacy is principally guaranteed under Section 37 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended),²⁴ and the Child Rights Act 2003 in its Section 8²⁵. Also, Nigeria has international obligation to respect, protect and fulfill the right to privacy of its citizens as contained in international human rights treaties it has ratified such as in art 17 of the ICCPR²⁶. The Concept of Individual Privacy has been prevalent since the inception of civilization²⁷. The concept of privacy is mentioned in the Code of Hammurabi in its Article 21 which states thus: 'If a man makes a breach into a house, one shall kill him in front of the breach and bury him in it'²⁸, the Bible²⁹, the Qur'an³⁰, Jewish Law³¹, and was present in classical Greece and ancient China³².

The right to privacy was defined by Brande in 1890, as 'the right to be let alone'³³, and described it as the most comprehensive of rights and the right most valued by civilized men³⁴. Section 37 of the Constitution of Nigeria states as follows: 'The privacy of citizens, their homes, correspondence, telephone conversations is hereby guaranteed and protected'³⁵. This Section of the Constitution explicitly covers privacy rights online as telephone conversation is clearly named and protected.

The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights contains no explicit provision on the right to privacy. However, the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child expressly guarantees a child's right to privacy under Article 10, protecting children from arbitrary or unlawful interference with their privacy, family, home, correspondence, honour, or reputation, subject to reasonable

¹⁵ Constitution (n¹²), s.37; African Charter (n¹³), art 11; Child Rights Acts 2003, s.8; International Covenant (n³), art 17.

¹⁶ *Ibid* s.39; *Ibid*, art 13, *Ibid* s.3, *Ibid*, art 19,

¹⁷ *Ibid* s.40; *Ibid*, arts 10; *Ibid* s.6, *Ibid* arts 21-22,

¹⁸ *Ibid* s.42, *Ibid* arts,2,28; *Ibid*, s.10, *Ibid*, arts 2, 25,26,27.

¹⁹ *Ibid*, s.33, *Ibid*, 4; *Ibid* s.3; *Ibid*, art 6.

²⁰ *Ibid*, s.18, *Ibid*, art 17; *Ibid*, s. 15; International Covenant on Economics (n⁴), art 13.

²¹ *Ibid*, s.16(3)(a) (b) & (e); *Ibid*, art 15; International Covenant on Economics (n⁴), art 6.

²² H McDermott, 'Application of the International Human Rights Law Framework in Cyberspace' in Dapo Akande and Others (eds), *Human Rights and 21st Century Challenges, Poverty, Conflict and the Environment* (Oxford University press 2020) 195 – 197.

²³ *Soering v the United Kingdom*, App No. 14038/88 (ECtHR, 07 July 1989)88; *Ireland v the United Kingdom* App No. 5310/71 (ECtHR 8 January 1978)163; *Hurri Laws v Nigeria*, Communication No. 225/98 (AComHPR, 6 November 2000)41; UNHRC, 'General Comment 20, Article 7 (Prohibition of Torture or other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (10 March 1992) para 3; CAT, General Comment 2 on the implementation of Article 2 by States parties (24 January 2008) CAT/C/GC/2 para 1 and 5).

²⁴ Constitution (n¹²), s.37.

²⁵ Child Right Act (n14), s.8.

²⁶ International Covenant (n³) art 17.

²⁷ A Rengel, 'privacy as an International Human Right and the Right to Obscurity in Cyberspace' (2014)(2)(2) *Groningen Journal of International Law* 37.

²⁸ Code of Hammurabi 1750 – 1700 BC, art 21; N B Lasson, 'The History of the Development of the Fourth Amendment to the United States Constitution' (Baltimore: John Hopkins Press 1937)14 – 15.

²⁹ R Hixson, *Privacy in public Society: Human Rights Conflicts* (New York: Oxford University press 1989)3; B Moore, *Privacy studies in Social and Cultural History* (New York: Random House 1984).

³⁰ Sahih Bukhari, Volume 1, Book 10, Number 509; Sahih Muslim, Book 020, Number 4727; Sunan Abu Dawud, Book 31, Number 4003.

³¹ J Rosen, *The Unwanted Gaze: The Destruction of privacy in America* (New York: Random House 2000)16.

³² Moore (n⁴⁵).

³³ L D Brandeis, 'The Right to Privacy' (1890)(4)(5) *Harvard Law Review* 193.

³⁴ S S Al-Fedaghe, 'The Right to be let Alone' and private Information, in CS fillipe and others (eds) *Enterprise Information Systems VII*. Spinger, Dordrecht <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5347-4_18> .

³⁵ Constitution (n¹²), s.37.

parental supervision and legal protection.³⁶ At the international level, Article 12 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights guarantees the right to privacy, protecting individuals from arbitrary interference with their privacy, family, home, or correspondence, and from attacks on their honour and reputation, with entitlement to legal protection against such violations³⁷. Article 17 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights guarantees that no person shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with their privacy, family, home, or correspondence, nor to attacks on their honour and reputation, and affirms the right to legal protection against such interference or attacks³⁸.

In Nigeria, the Nigeria Data Protection Act provides a comprehensive framework for personal data protection, aiming to safeguard constitutional privacy rights, regulate the processing of personal data, and promote secure data-processing practices³⁹. The Cybercrimes Act establishes a legal framework for protecting personal data in Nigeria by criminalizing privacy-violating acts, including unlawful access to computer systems⁴⁰, intercepting electronic messages, E-mails, Electronic money transfer⁴¹, willful misdirection of Electronic Messages⁴², unlawful interception⁴³. Other laws in Nigeria having provisions concerning the right to privacy are: the Child Rights Act 2003 in its Section 8, 142(9), 112(9) and 205(2)⁴⁴; Evidence Act 2011 in its Sections 183, 184, 186, 187, 191 and 192⁴⁵; Freedom of Information Act 2011 in its Sections 14 and 15⁴⁶ National Health Act,⁴⁷ Credit Reporting Act 2017⁴⁸, National Identity Management Act⁴⁹, Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act⁵⁰, HIV and AIDs (Anti-Discriminatory) Act⁵¹ Consumer Code of Practice Regulation⁵², Consumer Protection Framework⁵³, Nigerian Communications Commission (Registration of Telephone Subscribers) Regulation⁵⁴, Guidelines for the Management of Personal Data by public institutions in Nigeria⁵⁵, and NCC Lawful Interception of Communications Regulations 2019⁵⁶.

The digital era, driven by the internet, social media, mobile services, and data-driven technologies, has increased the collection and processing of personal and corporate information, heightening concerns over the fundamental right to privacy⁵⁷. In specific, the digital era or the cyber world has generated opportunities and advanced the right to privacy in Nigeria.

In the cyberworld, privacy rights are being protected via the use of technologies such as Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs),⁵⁸ the most important one being encryption. Encryption is a security tool that protects messages by converting them into unreadable cipher text accessible only to intended recipients, who can decrypt them back into readable form. Although it may be targeted by

³⁶ African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child 1990, art 10.

³⁷ Universal Declaration (n²), art 12.

³⁸ International Covenant (n3) art 17.

³⁹ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.1(1)(a) – (c).

⁴⁰ Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention) Act 2015, s.6.

⁴¹ *Ibid*, s.9.

⁴² *Ibid*, s.11.

⁴³ *Ibid*, s.12.

⁴⁴ Child Rights (n¹⁴), ss.8, 112(9), 142(9) and 205(2).

⁴⁵ Evidence Act 2011, ss.183, 184, 185, 187, 191 and 192.

⁴⁶ Freedom of Information Act 2011, ss.14 and 15.

⁴⁷ National Health Act 2011, s.26.

⁴⁸ Credit Reporting Act 2017, ss.6 and 9.

⁴⁹ National Identity Management Act 2007, s.26.

⁵⁰ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2019 s.34(6).

⁵¹ HIV and AIDs (Anti-Discriminating) Act 2014, s.13(1)

⁵² Consumer Code of Practice Regulation 2007, ss.34 – 38.

⁵³ Consumer Protection Framework 2016 para 2.6 – 2.6.2 and 3.1.

⁵⁴ NCC Registration of Telephone Subscribers Regulation 2011, s.9.

⁵⁵ Guidelines for the Management of Personal Data by public Institutions in Nigeria 2020.

⁵⁶ NCC Lawful Interception of Communications Regulations 2019.

⁵⁷ United Nations, 'The Right to privacy in the Digital Age (United nations 1st November 2013) <<https://www.ohchr.org/en/stores/2013/right-privacy-digital-age>> accessed 27 August, 2024.

⁵⁸ Tech-FAQ, 'Technologies that can help Protect your Privacy' (Tech-FAQ) <<https://www.tech.faq.com/technologies-you-can-use-to-protect-your-privacy-html>> accessed 27th August, 2024.

ransomware, it remains essential for ensuring data protection and security⁵⁹. Encryption is used for e-mails, instant messages, and Virtual Private Network (VPN)⁶⁰.

Other Privacy Enhancing Technologies Anonymous, proxies used to create a barrier between a computer and the web making it impossible for anyone to access the computer's IP address: remailers, such are used to hide main e-mail address; the Onion Router (Tor) used for online anonymity using volunteer servers⁶¹. The cyberworld has also enhanced and created awareness of the right to privacy in Nigeria via the internet and various social media platforms⁶². Digital technologies like CCTV and surveillance tools allow remote monitoring and security, while the cyber ecosystem supports privacy-enhancing services such as online education, e-commerce, and telemedicine that enable users to access information and services with anonymity and discretion⁶³. Flutter wave, piggy vest, paystick, ulesson and my paddi are a few examples of such online-based businesses and services owned by Nigerians and used in Nigeria.

Conversely, the right to privacy, often called the 'right to be let alone' is frequently violated in cyberspace, as cybercriminals exploit platform vulnerabilities and digital services retain and sometimes disclose personal data without users' consent⁶⁴. Similarly, Privacy in Nigeria's cyberspace is threatened by unsolicited messages from telecoms, marketers, and apps, as well as by security agencies conducting unlawful searches of individuals' phones both in public and at home⁶⁵.

Cyberspace in Nigeria has facilitated both new and existing crimes, including hacking, phishing, cyberbullying, espionage, child pornography, piracy, identity and credit card theft, spamming, cryptocurrency scams, and other online fraud⁶⁶.

Unauthorized cyber surveillance by government agencies accessing personal data from institutions like the Nigerian Identity Management Commission, banks, and telecoms without consent poses a major privacy threat, often violating rights and being used to suppress dissent, hinder journalism, and weaken democracy⁶⁷.

b. Right to Freedom of Expression

In Nigeria, the right to freedom of expression is protected under Section 39 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and reinforced by Article 9 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, guaranteeing individuals the freedom to hold, receive, and share opinions and information without interference⁶⁸; section 39(2) grants individuals the right to own and operate media for sharing information and opinions, but restricts ownership of television or wireless broadcasting stations to the government or those authorized by the president under conditions set by the National Assembly⁶⁹.

It is instructive to note that the right to freedom of expression could be exercised via spoken words, use of social media platforms and online apps, newspaper articles and other publications, radio and television broadcasts. The right to operate a television or wireless broadcasting station in Nigeria can only be exercised with presidential authorization, subject to conditions established by an Act of the National Assembly.⁷⁰

⁵⁹ D Rafter, 'What is Encryption and How Does it protect your Data?' (Norton, 15th arch 2022) <<https://US.norton.com/blog/privacy/what-is-encryption#>> accessed 27 August, 2024.

⁶⁰ Tech-FAQ (n73).

⁶¹ *Ibid.*

⁶² F Olobu, 'Nigeria: Data privacy and protection under Nigerian Law (Mondaq, 19 February 2020) para 15.3 <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/privacy-protection-under-the-nigeria-law#ftnrsf30>> accessed 28 September 2022.

⁶³ J Bleiberg and D M West, 'Little Discussed Ways that Technology Enhanced privacy (TechTank 26th May 2015) <<https://www.brookings.edu/blog/techtank/2015/05/26/little-discussed-ways-that-technolo-enhancees-privacy/>> accessed 27 August 2024.

⁶⁴ L Lessing, Code: Version 2.0 (Basic Books 2006) 203.

⁶⁵ B Ikwuegbu, 'Privacy Rights in Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges in the Digital Eta', <<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365613162>> accessed 27 August 2024.

⁶⁶ B A Omodunbi and Others, 'Cyber-crimes in Nigeria: Analysis, Detection and prevention (2016)(1) *FUOYE Journal of Engineering and Technology* 37 – 38.

⁶⁷ J Odalubu, 'Digital Authorization in Nigeria (The Legal Nuggests Limited 30 November, 2011) <<https://www.legalnuggests.com/digital-authoritarision-in-Nigeria-by-juliet-odalubu/>> 27 August, 202.

⁶⁸ Constitution (n¹²), s.39(1).

⁶⁹ *Ibid.*, s.39(2).

⁷⁰ *Ibid.*

Article 9 of the Charter states that: ‘Every individual shall have the right to receive information. Every individual shall have the right to express and disseminate his opinions within the law’.⁷¹ Internationally, the right to freedom of expression is protected by the UDHR and the ICCPR, with Article 19 of the UDHR the freedom to hold opinions and to seek, receive, and share information across any media without interference.⁷²

Article 19(1) and (2) of the ICCPR guarantees everyone the right to hold opinions without interference and the right to freedom of expression, including the freedom to seek, receive, and share information and ideas across all borders through any medium.

The right to freedom of expression and opinion applies online as it applies offline. This is *in tandem* with the UN Human Rights Council Resolution which affirmed that International Human Rights Laws apply in cyberspace⁷³. Provisions on freedom of expression in Nigeria’s CFRN, the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights, the ICCPR, and the UDHR are technologically neutral, applying online and offline. The UN Human Rights Committee’s General Comment No. 34 affirms that Article 19(2) of the ICCPR explicitly protects internet-based communications⁷⁴; it urges states to take all necessary measures to promote the independence of new media emerging from information and communication technologies (ICT)⁷⁵; and to take into account both the differences and points of convergence in print and broadcast media on the one hand, and the internet in the other hand⁷⁶.

Online or digital expression involves sharing information and opinions via the internet and platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, X, Instagram, and TikTok. In Nigeria, this right is protected under Sections 39 of the CFRN, subject to reasonable restrictions for defense, public safety, order, morality, health, or protecting others’ rights.

In *Shreya Singhal v Union of India*⁷⁷, the Indian Supreme Court upheld online free speech ruling that freedom of expression on the internet is protected under the Indian Constitution and clarifying intermediary liability under the Information Technology Act 2000. Similarly in *Valdelomar Sibaya v Costa Rican Superintendence of Telecommunication*⁷⁸, regarding the right to freedom of expression online, the Costa Rican Supreme Court recognized that Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are essential for communication, democracy, and access to fundamental rights, emphasizing that the right to access the internet is a key component of exercising freedoms like expression, information, education, e-democracy, and government transparency⁷⁹.

Access to internet or worldwide web facilitates the exercise of the right to freedom of expression, including right to hold opinion, and to receive and impart information and ideas. The exercise of this right via online ought not be interfered save in the case of limitations imposed by law and are justifiable in a democratic society. The European Court of Human Rights has held in *Kalda v Estonia*⁸⁰ that the right of the applicant – a prisoner-to freedom of expression had been violated through the refusal to grant him access to the internet to visit websites containing legal information, as this had breached his right to receive information.

In Kenya, a High Court in *Geoffrey Andare v Attorney General*⁸¹ found a provision criminalizing ‘grossly offensive’ statements and false statements that are annoying, inconvenient, or causing needless anxiety, to be unconstitutional because it was vague and unjustifiably limited freedom of expression. Geoffrey Andare’s Facebook post accusing Titus Kuria of misconduct led Kuria to file a criminal complaint under Section 29 of Kenya’s Information and Communication Act. While the case was pending, Andare challenged Section 29, and the High Court ruled it unconstitutional for being vague and unjustifiably limiting freedom of expression’.

⁷¹ African Charter (n¹³), art 9.

⁷² Universal Declaration (n²), art 9.

⁷³ United Nation Human Rights Council (n⁹).

⁷⁴ United Nations Human Rights Committee General Comment No. 34, para 12.

⁷⁵ *Ibid*, para 15.

⁷⁶ *Ibid*, para 19.

⁷⁷ (2013) 12 S.C. 73.

⁷⁸ Costa-Rica-Exp, 17-000191-0007-Co.

⁷⁹ *Ibid*.

⁸⁰ Application No. 17429/10.

⁸¹ Petition No. 149/2015.

The court held that terms like ‘grossly offensive’, ‘indecent’, and ‘annoyance’ in the Act were vague and subjective, allowing judicial officers wide discretion, and cited *Sunday Times v United Kingdom* to conclude that this created an unconstitutionally broad and uncertain criminal standard⁸².

In Nigeria, the Court of Appeal in *Solomon Okedara v Attorney General*⁸³ upheld Section 24(1) of Nigeria’s Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act 2015, rejecting claims that it was vague or overbroad and confirming it does not violate Sections 36(12), 39, or 45 of the Constitution, while emphasizing that freedom of thought and expression remains a paramount constitutional right⁸⁴. The case of *The Incorporated Trustees of Paradigm Initiative for Information Technology Development v The Attorney General of the Federation*⁸⁵, the court of Appeal in Lagos also dismissed an appeal which challenged the constitutionality of Section 24(1) of the Cybercrimes Act 2015 for lacking in merit. However, in *Incorporated Trustees of Laws and Rights Awareness Initiatives v Nigeria*,⁸⁶ the ECOWAS court held that Section 24 of the Nigerian Cybercrimes Act, 2015 violated the right to freedom of expression. It is instructive to note, however, that the said section has been amended and the aspect that offends the right to freedom of expression has been deleted.

c. Other Rights Implicated in Cyberspace

i. The right to Peaceful Assembly and Association.

The right to freedom of Assembly and Association is guaranteed in Nigeria under Section 40 of the CFRN 1999,⁸⁷ Articles 10 & 11 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Right (Ratification and Enforcement) Act 1983⁸⁸; it is also protected under Articles 21 & 22 of the ICCPR 1966⁸⁹ and Article 20 of the UDHR⁹⁰. Though, the Constitution, the African Charter, the ICCPR and the UDHR, did not make reference to the internet or cyberspace, they provide a proper framework which guarantee the right to freedom of assembly and association for everyone⁹¹. There is now a broad understanding and well-established international position that the right to freedom of peaceful assembly and association applies equally online as offline⁹². The special rapporteur Maina Kial, called upon states in 2012 report (A/HRC/20/27) ‘to recognize that the rights to freedom of peaceful assembly and of association can be exercised through technologies including through the internet.

Resolutions 21/16⁹³ and 24/5⁹⁴ of the Human Rights Council on the rights to freedom of peaceful assembly and of association reiterate the important role of new information and communications technologies in enabling and the facilitating the enjoyment of the rights to freedom of peaceful assembly and association⁹⁵. The cyberspace as well as the internet is a tool and a space in which one may exercise the right to freedom of peace assembly and association⁹⁶.

Cyberspace can serve as a platform for protests, exemplified by January 18, 2012, when 115,000 websites including Reddit, English Wikipedia, Google, Mozilla, and Flickr protested SOPA and PIPA by going dark, prompting 3 million emails to Congress and over 24 million related tweets in 16 hours⁹⁷.

In Nigeria, social media has become a major platform for civic mobilization, as seen in the #EndSARS and #EndBadGovernance movements, which combined online and offline activism against police brutality and poor governance. However, the state severely violated fundamental rights

⁸² *Ibid*, para 77

⁸³ CA/L/174/18

⁸⁴ Digital Rights Lawyers Initiative, ‘An Overview of Online Expression as a Digital Right’ (Digital Rights Initiative 2020)16

⁸⁵ CA/L/556/2017

⁸⁶ ECW/CCJ/JUD/31/18

⁸⁷ Constitution (n¹²), s.40

⁸⁸ African Charter (n¹³), arts 10 & 11

⁸⁹ International Covenant (n³), art 21 & 22

⁹⁰ Universal Declaration (n²), art 20

⁹¹ Council of Europe ‘Draft Report on the Freedom of Assembly and Association: MSI – INT (2010)08 rev 2(11 May 2015) <<https://rm.coe.in/draft-report-on-freedom-of-assmby-and-association>> accessed 29 August 2024

⁹² Special Rapporteur on the Right to Freedom of Peaceful Assembly and of Association 2012 – Report (A/HRC)20/27

⁹³ Resolution A/HRC/RES/21/16

⁹⁴ Resolution A/HRC/RES/24/S

⁹⁵ Council of Europe (n¹⁰⁶)2

⁹⁶ *Ibid*, 5

⁹⁷ Public Outcry Over Antiparacy Bills Began as Groot-Roots <https://www.mytimes.com/2012/01/20/technology/public-outcry-over-antiparacy-bills-began-as-grass-roots-grumbling.html?pagewated=1&ref=technology&r=0>

during these protests, including freedoms of expression, assembly, personal security, and protection from torture⁹⁸. The ECOWAS Court of Justice held that the Federal Government of Nigeria violated the human rights of Obianuju Catherine Udeh and two others, breaching Articles 1, 4, 6, 9, 10, and 11 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights. The violations concerned the rights to life, personal security, freedoms of expression, assembly and association, prohibition of torture, the state's duty to investigate, and the right to an effective remedy⁹⁹.

ii. The Right to Freedom of Religion

This right is protected in Nigeria under Section 38 of the CFRN 1999 (as amended)¹⁰⁰, Article 8 of the African Charter on Human Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act,¹⁰¹ and Section 7 of the CRA¹⁰².

Section 38 of the Nigerian Constitution guarantees every person the freedom of thought, conscience, and religion, including the right to change their belief and to practice, manifest, and propagate it individually or collectively, in public or private¹⁰³.

On its part, the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act guarantees the right to freedom of religion in Article 8 as follows: 'Freedom of conscience, the profession and free practice of religion shall be guaranteed. No one may, subject to law and order, be submitted to measures restricting the exercise of these freedoms'¹⁰⁴. Section 7 of CRA guarantees every child the freedom of thought, conscience, and religion, while assigning parents or guardians the duty to guide the child's exercise of these rights in their best interest, with the child's religious upbringing being a paramount consideration in custody, guardianship, or adoption matters¹⁰⁵.

International and regional frameworks including UN Human Rights Council Resolution A/HRC/RES/32/13, the African Union Peace and Security Council's 2024 position on ICTs in cyberspace, and the UN General Assembly's 2021 Report of the Group of Governmental Experts on Responsible State Behaviour in Cyberspace (A/76/135, para. 36) affirm that municipal and international human rights laws apply in cyberspace, including Nigeria. Consequently, provisions of Section 38 and Section 7 of the CFRN, Article 8 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, and the CRA extend to Nigeria's digital space. Having ratified the ICCPR, Nigeria is obligated under international law to respect, protect, and fulfill its provisions, including Article 18, which guarantees freedom of thought, conscience, and religion¹⁰⁶, it further states that this right includes the freedom to have or to adopt a religion or belief of his choice, and freedom, either individually or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief in worship, observance, practice and teaching¹⁰⁷. No one shall be subjected to coercion which will impair his freedom to have or to adopt a religion or belief of his choice¹⁰⁸. The freedom to manifest one's religion or beliefs maybe subject only to such limitations as are prescribed by law and are necessary to protect public safety, order, health or morals or the fundamental rights and freedoms of others¹⁰⁹.

Freedom of religion in Nigeria is exercised online via platforms like Facebook, X, Instagram, WhatsApp, and YouTube, with churches such as Deeper Life Bible Church, Living Faith Church, Dunamis Church, and Assemblies of God Church streaming services. The state must ensure access to the internet and ICTs to protect this right.

Human rights guaranteed under International law that are also relevant for the protection of the practice of religion in cyberspace include: the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion¹¹⁰;

⁹⁸ S. Odeniyi, 'Federal Government Violated End SAARS protests' Rights – ECOWAS Court (Punch Newspaper 10th July 2024) <punchng.com> accessed 29th August, 2024

⁹⁹ *Ibid*

¹⁰⁰ Constitution (n¹²), s.28

¹⁰¹ African Charter (n¹³), art 8

¹⁰² Child's Right Act (n³⁰), s.7

¹⁰³ Constitution (n¹²), s.38

¹⁰⁴ African Charter (n¹³), art 8

¹⁰⁵ Child Rights' Act (n³), s. 7

¹⁰⁶ International Covenant (n³), art 18(1)

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid*

¹⁰⁸ *Ibid*, art 18(2)

¹⁰⁹ *Ibid*, art 18(3)

¹¹⁰ Universal Declaration (n²), art 18; International Covenant (n³), art 18

right to freedom of opinion and expression in Articles 19 of the UDHR 1948 and ICCPR 1966¹¹¹; prohibition of Advocacy of National, Racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence in Art 20 of ICCPR¹¹², right to privacy in Articles 12 of UDHR and 17 ICCPR¹¹³; and the right to freedom of assembly and association in Articles 20 of UDHR and 21, 22 of ICCPR¹¹⁴.

The UN Special Rapporteur on freedom of religion or belief has raised concerns regarding the wide dissemination of hate speech online targeting religious groups, including anti-Muslim and anti-Semitic hatred and conspiracy theories¹¹⁵.

iii. Right to Freedom against Discrimination

The internet's borderless nature makes online discrimination a global issue, requiring coordinated national, regional, and international action, as it involves denigrating or excluding people based on race, gender, sexual orientation, age, disability, religion, or belief through various digital media.

Discrimination in cyberspace can be direct, such as algorithmic or design-based bias. Algorithmic discrimination arises when biases embedded in codes and machine learning or AI systems systematically disadvantage specific individuals or groups¹¹⁶. Discrimination by design occurs when a website's structure inherently enables bias. For example, Roommates.com required users to select preferences for gender, sexual orientation, and family status from dropdown menus to find matches, effectively embedding discrimination into its functionality, raising issues under the Fair Housing Act¹¹⁷, which prohibits discrimination concerning the sale, rental, and financing of housing base on race, religion, national origin, sex (as amended) handicap and family status. In *Fair Housing Council v Roommates.com LLC*¹¹⁸, the United States Court of Appeals for the Ninth Circuit held that Roommates.com was immune under the Communications Decency Act for merely publishing users' additional comments. However, it was not protected where it materially contributed to the content's unlawfulness by designing questionnaires that required disclosure of sex, sexual orientation, and family status, restricting searches based on those criteria, and operating a matching system that paired users accordingly¹¹⁹. However, the appellate court reversed the lower court, ruling that restricting people from choosing compatible roommates would seriously invade privacy, autonomy, and security. It also noted that bias can arise indirectly through user behavior on platforms like social media, forums, and online games, raising complex questions about the responsibilities of tech companies under human rights law, contracts, or regulatory frameworks?¹²⁰

Algorithmic discrimination is hidden and often unnoticed by users, while user-generated bias on platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube is visible. Despite this, platform liability remains uncertain, as they are not traditional publishers, even though they influence and regulate online information¹²¹. Online discrimination, often fueled by hate or prejudice, closely overlaps with hate speech, which promotes or justifies hatred, violence, or discrimination.

The provisions of national, regional and international human rights law on the right to freedom from discrimination apply in cyberspace as they apply in the physical space. This position is supported by the UN Human Rights Council Resolution A/HRC/RES/13 on the promotion and enjoyment of human rights on the internet. Accordingly in Nigeria, Section 42 of the CFRN¹²², Article 2 of the African Charter,¹²³ Section 10 of the CRA¹²⁴ guarantee freedom from discrimination. Section 42 of the

¹¹¹ *Ibid*, art 19; *Ibid*, art 19

¹¹² International Covenant (n³), art 20

¹¹³ Universal Declaration (n²), art 12; International Covenant (n³), art 17

¹¹⁴ *Ibid*, art 20; *Ibid*, art 21 & 22

¹¹⁵ United States Commission on International Religious Freedom, 'Fact – sheet protecting religious freedom online' <<https://www.uscirf.gov/files/2021-12/>>

¹¹⁶ P Lopez, 'Bias Does not Equal Bias: A Socio-Technical Typology of Bias in Data – Based Algorithm Systems' (2021)(10)(4) Internet Policy Review 34

¹¹⁷ United States Fair Housing Act 1968, ss. 800 – 808

¹¹⁸ 521 F.3d 1157 (9th Cir 2008); 666F.3d 1216

¹¹⁹ *Ibid*

¹²⁰ UN Human Right Council, 'Report of the Special Rapporteur on the protection and promotion of the freedom of opinion 2016, p.3

¹²¹ L K Barocas, 'Designing Against Discrimination in online market' (2017)(32) Berkeley Technology Law Journal 1183

¹²² Constitution (n¹²), s. 42

¹²³ African Charter (n¹³), art 2

Nigerian Constitution prohibits discrimination, ensuring that no citizen is unfairly subjected to disadvantages or granted privileges based solely on their community, ethnicity, place of origin, sex, religion, or political opinion¹²⁵; by section 42 (2) of the Constitution, ‘No citizen of Nigeria shall be subjected to any disability or deprivation merely on reason of the circumstances of his birth’¹²⁶.

It is instructive to note that the right to freedom from discrimination guaranteed under section 42 of the CFRN 1999 appears to be absolute as it is not subject to Section 45 of the Constitution which creates limitations to some of the fundamental rights provided under chapter four of the Constitution.

- iv. The rights to life, right to dignity of human person, right to freedom of movement and right to work and so on, may also be implicated in cyberspace.

3.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Nigeria’s human rights protections, including those in its Constitution, the African Charter, the CRA, and international treaties, apply equally in cyberspace. UN and African Union bodies affirm that states must respect, protect, and ensure these rights online. However, many online users are unaware of these protections, resulting in frequent rights violations without recourse.

Key human rights in Nigeria’s and global cyberspace include freedom of expression, privacy, peaceful assembly, freedom from discrimination, freedom of thought and religion, internet access, work, education, and political participation. These rights are exercised or violated through websites, social media, apps, and other ICTs.

It is recommended that Nigeria’s Constitution particularly Chapter Four, be amended to explicitly include a ‘right to access the internet’ or ‘right to connect’, guaranteeing universal access to information technology and the internet, so individuals can fully exercise their human rights in cyberspace without undue restriction.

¹²⁴ Child Rights’ Act (n³⁰), s. 10

¹²⁵ Constitution (n¹²), s. 42(1)(a) & (b)

¹²⁶ *Ibid*, s. 42(2)